

length/greatest width = 1.4.

5 males: length = 1,150-1,248 μm , stylet = 16.5 μm , length/greatest width = 150-175, spicule = 11.5 μm .

20 second-stage juveniles: length = 42040 μm , length/greatest width =

25-27, length/esophagus length = 3.44.0, length/tail length = 6.0-6.5, stylet = 11.5-12 μm .

Measurements and the perineal pattern of females indicated the species is *Meloidogyne graminicola* Golden and

Birchfield. The nematode is found in Orissa, Assam, and Tripura States of India; Bangladesh; Thailand; and Louisiana, United States. This is the first record of the nematode in West Bengal. □

Control of rice root nematode

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Rice root nematode *Hirschmaniella oryzae* is an important rice pest in India and other countries. Nematode populations are high in flooded, heavy alluvial soils.

Nursery and root-soak pesticide appli-

cations were tested for nematode control on IR20 at two locations in Tamil Nadu in 1980-81 (see table). Treatments were replicated thrice in 4-m² nursery beds and 2 × 1 m plots at 20 × 15 cm spacing.

Root samples were collected at monthly intervals until harvest by randomly uprooting one plant from each plot. Nematodes separated from the roots by the Baermann pan technique were counted.

Grain yield, plant height, root length, and root weight were recorded.

Nematode populations ranged from 18 to 270 per 5 g of root examined from different treatments (see table).

Application of carbofuran 3% G at 1 kg ai/ha in the nursery at sowing, followed by phenamiphos or carbosulfone 0.2% root soak, significantly reduced nematode populations and increased grain yield. □

Effect of pesticides on rice root nematode at 2 locations, Tamil Nadu, India.^a

Nematicide		Aduthurai					Sirugamani				
Seedbed	Seedling root soak	Popu- lation (TV)	Plant ht (cm)	Roots		Grain yield (kg/2 m ²)	Popu- lation (crv)	Plant ht (cm)	Roots		Grain yield ² (kg/2 m ²)
				Length (cm)	Weight (g)				Length (cm)	Weight (g)	
Carbofuran 3% G 1 kg ai/ha	Carbosulfone 24 EC at 0.2% concn	6.35	94.0	30.0	27.3	0.67	7.57	77.7	32.3	28.0	0.75
Carbofuran 3% G 1 kg ai/ha	Phenamiphos 40 EC at 0.2% concn	7.17	94.3	30.3	19.0	0.71	5.70	82.3	36.7	30.0	0.78
Metham sodium 77.5 kg ai/ha	Dimethoate 30 EC at 0.2%	9.90	84.0	23.7	17.0	0.42	8.10	79.3	33.0	23.3	0.45
Metham sodium 77.5 kg ai/ha	-	10.20	89.7	27.7	25.3	0.41	9.87	78.3	32.0	21.7	0.47
Untreated check C. D.		11.63	81.7	31.3	20.0	0.41	13.20	70.7	28.7	22.0	0.39
		1.33	N.S.	4.0	3.7	0.061	1.33	6.0	4.57	N.S.	0.06

^aMeans for 3 replications. ^bTV = transformed values of $\sqrt{x+0.5}$ where 'x' stands for the nematode population.

Pest management and control WEEDS

Effect of planting density and submergence level on weed density in rice fields

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Effect of planting density and submergence level on weed density was recorded at 70 sites in Nadia District, West Bengal, during the 1981 wet season. Sites were planted with medium-duration improved rice varieties.

1. Relationship between planting density and weed density.